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The Journal of Information Resource Management is a peer-reviewed journal of the Nigerian Library Association, Niger State chapter that publishes articles once a year; articles are received throughout the year. Specifically, the journal covers the areas of Library Science, Information Science, Knowledge Management and allied disciplines for the purpose of promoting interdisciplinary studies in Library/ Information related disciplines. The goal of the journal is to bring together researchers and practitioners from academia and industry to focus on areas of LIS exploration.

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John, M.A. Cash prize for the best institute of management student. *National Concord*, May 20, 1987, P9

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EDITORIAL

Journal of Information and Resource Management (JIRM) is a publication of the Niger State Chapter of the Nigerian Library Association (NLA). This current edition is Volume 9 Number 1. On behalf of the Editorial Board, I wish to express our sincere appreciation to Almighty Allah for His continued support and guidance towards publishing the edition. It is also pertinent to acknowledge our contributors for their concerns and affection to publish with us.

The painstaking efforts of our peer reviewers are noted and highly commended. The support from the parent body of the Nigerian Library Association (NLA) Niger State Chapter under the commendable leadership of Dr. Fatimah Jibril Abduldayan (CLN) is meritorious. It is imperative to also recognize the wonderful efforts and good working relationship of the Editorial Board members, particularly Dr. Sadiat Adetoro Salau, the Managing Editor who is always ready to accept and carry out the responsibility. On a sad note, we lost Dr. Stella A. Onwukanjo, the Assistant Editor-in-Chief late last year. Her demise is a great loss, may God console her family.

This edition of the journal has twelve articles whose titles cut across diverse areas of librarianship. The first article revolved around the use of Adaptive Equipment Technology for Supporting Disabled Persons at the Federal University of Technology, Minna Library Environment by Okechukwu, Emmanuel Munachi, Chuks-Ibe, Prisca Oluchi, Amina Abubakar Saidu and Halimah Nene Tauheed. The second paper by Adejo, Alhaji Augustine addressed Availability and Utilisation of Digital Library System in Kashim Ibrahim Library, Ahmadu Bello University Zaria. Another article is Use of Academic Social Networking Sites Among Lecturers in Nigerian Defence Academy, Kaduna written by Safiya Garba Mohammed. In their paper, Edimeh, Augustine, Musa, Hussaini & Abdulkadir, Mustapha Gana discussed on Availability and Awareness of Virtual Referencing Services in Selected Academic Libraries in Niger State.

Changing Roles of Libraries in the Digital Age: The Past, Present and the Future is the fifth article written by Fatimah Jibril Abduldayan (PhD, CLN), Mohammed Sulaiman Nuhu and Harithat Oyiza Jibril. The article by Dr. S.O. Akande, Dr. Funmi K. Olajide-Williams and Victoria A. Ayoola centred on the Effect of Educational Cartoon on Learning the English Language among Private Primary School Pupils in Ibarapa East Local Government Area, Oyo State, Nigeria.

The paper on Design of an Academic Library for Effective Learning, Research and National Development was co-researched by Mohammed, M. S. (CLN), Faniyi, S. S. (CLN) and Aliyu, M. I. (CLN). In their study, Samuel Oghenerukevwe Egbo, Ossom, Nsemeke Edet, and Juliet C. Alex-Nmecha examined Digital Intelligence as a Predictor for driving the Utilisation of Artificial Intelligence in Academic Libraries in Rivers State.

The study of Influence of Online Information Resources Accessibility and Information Seeking Behaviour on Academic Activities of Students of Colleges of Education in Nigeria was conducted by Abubakar Mohammed Bida (CLN), Prof. Juliana N. Udensi (CLN), Prof. Philip, U. Akor, and Dr. Micheal A. Obaje. In their research, Baba Patience, Evarest Chibuogwu Madu and Oserada Wilson determined the Influence of Provision of Electronic Journals and User Satisfaction on Job Productivity of Academic Staff of Selected Federal Polytechnics in North-Central, Nigeria.

The eleventh paper determined Librarians' Effective Communication Skills and Service Delivery in Federal University Libraries in South-South Nigeria by Benadette C. N. Ukaegbu (PhD, CLN) and Ifeyinwa Josephine Udumukwu (PhD, CLN). In their article, Ogbu, S.E, and Folarimi examined the Role of Libraries in the Development of Eco-Tourism in Nigeria.

Finally, I wish to once again thank all those who have contributed to the success of the production of this edition. I do hope that you will continue to patronize our Journal (JIRM). I wish you all a happy and resourceful reading.

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